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XALQARO JURNALI**

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ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД**

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TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД LANGUAGE, EDUCATION, TRANSLATION

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СПЕЦИФИКА ГАСТРОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ И СЛОВООБРАЗОВАНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ НЕМЕЦКИХ ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЧЕСКИХ ИСТОЧНИКАХ И СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ СЕТЯХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В исследовании изучаются лексико-семантические особенности немецкой гастрономической лексики с учётом тематической классификации. В статье также акцентируется внимание на особенностях орфографической адаптации при заимствовании лексики в современный немецкий язык. Исследователь описывает лексикографическое своеобразие немецкой кулинарной лексики в зависимости от тематической дифференциации. Автор статьи акцентирует особое внимание на анализе классификационных параметров исследования гастрономической лексики в ракурсе общей лексики, связанной с едой и кулинарией, определенных типов еды, гастрономических трендов. Декодирование имплицитных показателей на лексико-семантическом уровне в ракурсе бытовых реалий становится актуальной проблемой исследования в связи с притоком новой лексики в состав активного словарного состава немецкого языка, интеграции кулинарного опыта в связи с процессами глобализации и различными экстралингвистическими факторами. Изучаются отдельные примеры на базе тематической классификации, а также особенности выражений и лексем из текстов кулинарных блогов, гастрономического дискурса. Исследователь акцентирует внимание на специфике представления словообразования. Затрагиваются проблемы телескопии, словосложения, суффиксации. При изучении компонентного состава гастрономической лексики учитываются этимологические данные,

включающие разъяснения топонимических компонентов, культурологических и социальных факторов.

Ключевые слова: кулинарный контекст, гастрономические реалии, лингвокультурологическое пространство, топонимы, орфографическая адаптация, деривационные особенности, тематические группы, бытовые реалии, заимствования, лексико-семантические лакуны.

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ZAMONAVIY NEMIS LEKSIKOGRAFIK MANBALARI VA IJTIMOIY TARMOQLARIDA GASTRONOMIK LEKSIKA VA SO'Z YASALISHINING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Tadqiqotda nemis gastronomik leksikasining leksik-semantik xususiyatlari tematik tasnifni hisobga olgan holda o'rganiladi. Maqolada, shuningdek, zamonaviy nemis tiliga leksika o'zlashtirilganda orfografik moslashuvning xususiyatlariga e'tibor qaratiladi. Tadqiqotchi nemis kulinar leksikasining tematik differentsiatsiyaga qarab leksikografik o'ziga xosligini tasvirlaydi. Maqola muallifi umumiy oziq-ovqat va kulinar bilan bog'liq leksika, oziq-ovqatning muayyan turlari, gastronomik trendlar nuqtai nazaridan gastronomik leksikani tadqiq qilishning tasnifiy parametrlarini tahlil qilishga alohida e'tibor qaratadi. Leksik-semantik darajadagi implitsit ko'rsatkichlarni turmush realiyalari nuqtai nazaridan dekodlash, nemis tilining faol lug'at tarkibiga yangi leksikaning kirib kelishi, globallashtirish jarayonlari va turli ekstralingvistik omillar bilan bog'liq holda kulinar tajribaning integratsiyasi munosabati bilan tadqiqotning dolzarb muammosiga aylanadi. Tematik tasnifga asoslangan alohida misollar, shuningdek, kulinar bloglar, gastronomik diskurs matnlaridagi iboralar va leksemalarning xususiyatlari o'rganiladi. Tadqiqotchi so'z yasashning o'ziga xosligiga e'tibor qaratadi. Teleskopiya, so'z birikmalari, suffiksatsiya muammolari ko'rib chiqiladi. Gastronomik leksikaning komponent tarkibini o'rganishda toponimik komponentlar, kulturologik va ijtimoiy omillarni tushuntirishni o'z ichiga olgan etimologik ma'lumotlar hisobga olinadi..

Kalit so'zlar: kulinar konteksti, gastronomik realliklar, lingvokulturologik makon, toponimlar, orfografik moslashuv, derivatsion xususiyatlar, tematik guruhlar, turmush realiyalari, o'zlashtirmalar, leksik-semantik lakunalar.

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SPECIFICITY OF GASTRONOMIC VOCABULARY AND WORD FORMATION IN MODERN GERMAN LEXICOGRAPHICAL SOURCES AND SOCIAL NETWORKS

ABSTRACT

The study examines the lexical and semantic features of German gastronomic vocabulary taking into account the thematic classification. The article also focuses on the features of orthographic adaptation when borrowing vocabulary into modern German. The researcher describes the lexicographic originality of German culinary vocabulary depending on thematic differentiation. The author of the article focuses on the analysis of the classification parameters of the study of gastronomic vocabulary in the context of general vocabulary related to food and cooking, certain types of food, and gastronomic trends. Decoding implicit indicators at the lexical and semantic level in the context of everyday realities is becoming an urgent research problem due to the influx of new vocabulary into the active vocabulary of the German language, the integration of culinary experience in connection with globalization processes and various extralinguistic factors. Individual examples are studied based on the thematic classification, as well as features of expressions and lexemes from the texts of culinary blogs and gastronomic discourse. The researcher focuses on the specifics of the presentation of word formation. The problems of telescoping, word composition, suffixation are touched upon. When studying the component composition of gastronomic vocabulary, etymological data are considered, including explanations of toponymic components, cultural and social factors.

Keywords: culinary context, gastronomic realities, linguacultural space, toponyms, orthographic adaptation, derivational features, thematic groups, everyday realities, borrowings, lexical-semantic gaps.

German neologisms are studied from a multi-level perspective and considering the influence of a number of extralinguistic factors [9, 20]. Additional information in dictionary entries pertaining to gastronomic vocabulary allows us to identify the specifics of dish composition, methods of preparation and presentation [5, 122].

In contemporary research, the concepts of intercultural communication or cross-cultural communication related to food, its various preparation methods, and advertising are frequently explored through the terms *culinary context* [2,

9], *gastronomic realities* [19, 62] and *gluttonic discourse* [3, 12] (or *gluttonic linguocultural space* [20, 203]).

Gastronomic discourse includes “mentifact” [1, 40]. This term refers to culturally significant concepts that are key elements of national consciousness, identity, and everyday characteristics of a specific linguocultural space [22, 355].

Lexical units and expressions used to describe eating habits, types of dishes, and nutrition play a crucial role in shaping the cultural worldview, reflecting the unique characteristics, traditions, and values of the German people [4, 10]. Modern linguocultural research confirms a sustained interest in discursive questions related to lexemes, expressions, and texts that reflect everyday life.

German words and expressions related to the thematic group “Food and related concepts”, richly represented in the contexts of dictionary sources, blogs, travel guides, catering advertisements, and everyday communication, serve as a powerful channel for transmitting linguaculture [16, 7]. This occurs both through simple mentions or listings of traditional dishes, snacks, sweets, and beverages, and through comments of a linguocultural nature, revealing new data about the realities of the German gastronomic world [10, 128].

However, despite the significant amount of research, the problem of decoding everyday realities remains relevant due to the influx of new vocabulary, the integration of culinary experience, and other reasons related to territorial, social, and economic factors [14, 21]. In this article, the author aims to identify approaches to filling lexico-semantic gaps that hinder the accurate perception of the foreign language context by participants in a speech act who are not native to German culture in the area under analysis.

Let's provide different examples of borrowings from the thematic group *general vocabulary related to food and cooking*: *Meal Prep* with the meaning food preparation in advance – a practice that allows you to optimize time and adhere to the principles of a healthy diet by preparing meals for several days in advance (“Sonntags mache ich immer Meal Prep für die ganze Woche” [18]); *Veggie-Day* – a practice where catering establishments offer exclusively meat-free dishes on a certain day of the week (“Donnerstag ist Veggie-Day in unserer Kantine” [18]); *Clean Eating* – a dietary system based solely on whole, minimally processed foods (“Sie ernährt sich nach dem Prinzip des Clean Eating” [18]); *Superfood* – products characterized by a high concentration of beneficial substances and unique properties that have a beneficial effect on the body (“Chiasamen sind ein echtes Superfood” [18]), etc. It should be noted that among the thematic group of neologisms describing specific types of food, a significant percentage of the vocabulary describes dietary dishes, as well as a healthy lifestyle and the transition to recyclable waste.

The influx of modern vocabulary into the German language is closely linked to processes of borrowing [11, 540], semantic derivation [17, 1109], and lexico-semantic adaptation [15, 23].

Germany actively pursues a policy to preserve the purity of the language. However, the penetration of Anglicisms into German-language vocabulary is becoming an everyday phenomenon, especially for young people [13, 81]. The most popular vocabulary for borrowing comes from thematic groups such as food, clothing, gender terms, and words from pop culture.

Cp. general vocabulary related to food and cooking as popular borrowings from English gastronomic vocabulary – *Foodporn* with the meaning attractive photos of various products, food, distributed on the internet (e.g., on social networks) to attract attention and entice with their appearance (“Dieser Kuchen ist purer Foodporn!” - example from the social network Facebook).

Often, when a word is borrowed, it undergoes lexico-semantic adaptation in the borrowing language. However, in the example above, the word only changed at the level of orthographic styling. In German, nouns are capitalized regardless of their position in the sentence, unlike in English.

Originally appearing in the late 70s of the XX century, the term *Foodporn* has significantly evolved in its semantics. Its emergence is associated with Rosalind Coward, an active member of the feminist movement, who used it in the 80s of the XX century to describe glossy images of food.

The real explosion of *foodporn's* popularity occurred in XXI with the emergence of a corresponding category on the popular photo platform.

Unlike culinary shows of the past, which were targeted at housewives, the modern image of food has become more glamorous and prestigious: famous actors, singers, and artists appear in popular shows and on the covers of leading magazines.

Thus, the word has acquired the semantics of demonstrating social status. Therefore, the influence of social factors on the transformation of the modern understanding of *foodporn* can be traced.

In an era when healthy eating has become one of the leading trends, people pay special attention to their diet. Well-known, new restaurants, cafes and other similar establishments, seeking to attract new customers, are responding to this demand by introducing special *Vegetarian* sections on the menu with dishes that do not include meat components, such as *Haugemachte Spinatknödel*, *Spinat mit zwei Spiegeleiern und Kartoffeln* and others.

Cp. also: *Zero Waste Küche* is a culinary philosophy that implies waste-free production and the use of all components of products (“In meiner Zero Waste Küche versuche ich, alles zu verwerten” [18]); *Proteinbombe* with the meaning a dish or product characterized by an extremely high protein content (“Quark mit Nüssen ist eine echte Proteinbombe” [18]); *Low-Carb* – a characteristic of products or diets with a reduced carbohydrate content. (“Ich mache gerade eine Low-Carb-Diät” [18]).

Derivational features of German lexemes related to food are closely intertwined with the general trends of German word formation, but also have their own specific features, reflecting the culture of nutrition, trends and

innovations in the gastronomic sphere. Let's list the main features of word formation of German gastronomic vocabulary:

I. One of the most common methods of word formation is composition (*Zusammensetzung*). This is the most productive way to form new words in German, and it is particularly popular in the field of food. Neologisms are formed by joining two or more words.

A) Determination + Verb (*Bestimmungswort + Verb*):

For example: *Smoothie-Mixen* (smoothie mixing, *Smoothie + Mixen*).

B) Determination + Determined (*Bestimmungswort + Grundwort*).

This model with parts of speech is considered the most common type.

For example: *Veggie-Burger* (vegetarian burger – model: *Veggie* from *Vegetarian + Burger*). *Superfood-Salat* (model: *Superfood + Salat*). *Meal-Prep* (food preparation in advance – model: *Meal + Prep* from preparation).

C) Adjective + Noun (*Adjektiv + Substantiv*):

For example: *Rohkostteller* (raw food plate – model: *Rohkost + Teller*).

Let's analyze the features of composition, also known as telescoping, in the field of food:

1) Reflection of culinary trends: Neologisms often reflect current trends, such as veganism, vegetarianism, gluten-free diets, etc.

2) Emphasizing health benefits: Many neologisms emphasize health benefits, using words like *Bio-*, *Superfood-*, *Clean Eating-*.

3) Use of Anglicisms: English words are often used, especially in the context of new gastronomic trends such as *vegan*, *low-carb*, *raw food*. This can lead to hybrid composites (a mixture of German and English elements).

II. Semantic Shift (*Semantische Verschiebung*). Existing words acquire new meanings in the context of food.

For example: *Bowl* (with the meaning “dish with food”, borrowed from English, originally meaning a bowl, a dish).

III. Morphemic method of word formation, despite being one of the most classic methods of derivation, has not lost its leading position in the formation of modern German [12, 70].

Formation of new words with prefixes and suffixes.

A) Prefixation:

For example: “*Bio-*” denotes the organic origin of the product. Compare: *Bio-Eier* (organic eggs).

B) Suffixation:

-*er/in*: Formation of nouns denoting persons engaged in something related to food. For example: *Foodblogger* (food blogger).

-*ig*: Formation of adjectives. For example: *zuckerhaltig* (containing sugar).

IV. Abbreviation and truncation (*Abkürzung und Kürzung*):

New words from gastronomic discourse can be formed by shortening existing words or phrases.

For example: *Foodie* (from “food” + suffix -ie, under the influence of the English language, denoting a person passionate about food). *Mealprepping* (from “meal preparation”, under the influence of English).

V. Conversion (Konversion): The transition of a word from one part of speech to another without changing its form.

Verbs can become nouns denoting a process or result. For example: *Das Snacken* (*snacking* from the verb *snacken*).

It is important to note that word formation is a dynamic process, and new trends may appear over time.

The analysis of the linguocultural component [7, 3] of restaurant menus in Germany was devoted to identifying and studying their linguistic features depending on extralinguistic factors [8, 50].

The main focus was on the lexical level of the German language, namely on the use of territorially marked components [21, 230] within the gastronomic discourse [6, 91].

The name of a city, country, village, region, street, body of water is intended to draw the attention of speech participants to the unique history of the emergence, manufacture of a particular dish in a specific geographical location. Let us illustrate this statement with examples from dictionaries:

1) inclusion of the names of states – *Bayerische Creme mit Beeren* (Bavarian cream with berries), *Bayerischer Sauerkrautsalat*, *Bayrischer Wurstsalat* (Bavarian sausage salad);

2) inclusion of the names of cities – *Hamburger Kuchen mit Mohn* (Hamburg poppy seed cake), *Berliner Braten im Topf* (Berlin roast in a pot), *Hamburg Suppe* (Hamburg soup), *Berliner Apfelkuchen* (Berlin apple cake), *Hamburger mit Thüringer Mohnkuchen* (Hamburg with Thuringian poppy seed cake), *Berliner Kartoffelsuppe* (Berlin potato soup), *Hamburger Kartoffelkuchen* (Hamburg potato cake), *Dresdner Eierschecke* (Dresden curd cake), *Düsseldorfer Senf* (Düsseldorf mustard)

3) inclusion of the names of mountain objects: mountains, ridges – *Thüringer Käsegrillies von Bienlein* (Thuringian cheese grillies from Bienlein), *Älplermagronen* (a dish consisting of garlic cloves, potatoes, bacon), *Thüringer Kartoffelpuffer* (Thuringian potato pancakes), *Thüringer Quark* (Thuringian quark);

4) inclusion of river names – *Rheinischer Sauerbraten*, etc.

The thematic group of German lexemes related to gastronomic trends: *Urban Gardening* with the meaning “growing vegetables, fruits and herbs in urban environments, for example, on balconies, roofs or in community gardens”. For example: “Urban Gardening ist ein toller Trend für mehr Nachhaltigkeit” [18] (“Urban Gardening is a great trend for more sustainability”); *Foodsharing* meaning “an initiative to reduce food waste based on the exchange of food between people”. Example: “Durch Foodsharing können wir Lebensmittelverschwendung reduzieren” [18] (“Through Foodsharing we can reduce food waste.”); *Craft Beer* – “a product of small, independent breweries,

which uses classic recipes and selected raw materials”. For example: “Ich probiere gerne neue Craft Beer Sorten” [18] (“I like to try new Craft Beer varieties”).

The thematic group of German lexemes related to funny and ironic neologisms: *Feierabendbier* meaning “a beer that is drunk after work to relax and unwind.” For example: “Nach der Arbeit gönne ich mir ein Feierabendbier” [18] (“After work I treat myself to an after-work beer”).

Conclusion.

Thus, based on the results of the above study on German lexis with food component, the following conclusions were drawn:

In a more precise understanding, mentifacts are lexical units that carry cultural meaning, often presented to participants in a speech act through metaphorical formations and referring the reader or listener to specific precedent situations, acting as symbols that allow the true meaning to be revealed. Culinary terms, enriched with German culturally specific realities, are formed through truncation, contraction, reduplication, morphemic changes, borrowing of a whole word or part of it from other languages and the German language itself. Gastronomic realities are particularly prevalent in social networks in the form of popular culinary blogs with advertising of products, numerous recipes, challenges in support of a healthy diet), where new lexical units and combinations are formed by native speakers. Undoubtedly, the realities specific to the German language can present difficulties for understanding and accurate translation due to implicit characteristics that are hidden from perception without primary decoding. Decoding the meaning can be done based on etymological features.

Summarizing, we can highlight the following features in terms of lexicosemantic and word-formation features of German neologisms in the field of food:

Firstly, the prevalence and dominance of telescoping (composition) as the main way to form new words.

Secondly, the increased influence of the English language on the lexical component of the German language. As a result of the analysis, the active use of Anglicisms and borrowings is noted, especially in relation to new trends.

Thirdly, an emphasis is revealed on health and conscious consumption of fresh, high-quality, biologically beneficial products. German contexts are often filled with lexical units relating to such thematic groups as healthy eating trends, organic products, and conscious consumption.

Fourthly, modern Internet blogs reflect vocabulary related to culinary innovations. New words appear to describe new dishes, culinary techniques and gastronomic concepts.

Fifthly, there is an increased use of colloquial and slang language. This trend is explained by the fact that neologisms can spontaneously or consciously arise in colloquial speech and spread quickly.

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